

HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN AZERBAIJAN**Elmira Huseynova***Ph.D.,**Western Caspian University**III parallel, 21 Ahmad Rajabli, Baku, AZE1072***Abstract**

The article deals with the history of learning foreign languages in Azerbaijan and covers the periods starting from the 8th century till the modern time. It touches on historical developments related to teaching foreign languages, and what is more, strategies utilized in different periods.

Additionally, the article also shows how historical, social, and religious situations impacted and shaped the approach to foreign language learning in Azerbaijan because the occupations Azerbaijan underwent determined the official language in the country, and forced people to learn those languages. The colonizers' languages and culture of teaching language played an important role in this process.

Keywords: strategy, foreign languages, history, teaching, methodology

Foreign language teaching is one of the most widespread and constantly changing areas, and it is impossible to imagine our modern globalized world without it. Currently, all countries and people are connected to each other in some way. This brings out the need to learn foreign languages and also causes interest in people and exploring other cultures. Thus, aforementioned makes people start searching for the answer to this question: "How can I learn a language quickly and effectively?" This prompts teachers to find answers to that question, too and as a result new teaching methodologies and strategies emerge. Although there are similar trends in foreign language teaching around the world, in fact, the history, economy, social situation and culture of each country affect this process and create certain differences. In this article, we will explore the history of language teaching in Azerbaijan starting from 8th century.

In the 8th century, Azerbaijan was invaded by Arab troops and became part of the Arab caliphate. For 8 centuries, Azerbaijan was under the influence of Islam religion and culture. Thus, Arabic became the language of science and communication among vast Muslim countries including Azerbaijan. Azerbaijanis gradually adopted the Arabic language along with the religion of the Arabs and used it in scientific, religious and literary works for a long time.

As a result of the reforms made by the tenth Umayyad Caliph Abdulmalik Hisham (685-705), during this period correspondence and records in government offices were only in Arabic, and the Azerbaijani officials working in government offices had to learn this language as well. During those years mosques weren't used for only prayer, they were also centers of learning. Kuran, religious sciences and the Arabic language were taught at mosques.

When we reached the twelfth century, the language of literature in Azerbaijan became Persian because it was a lingua franca in that period. Thus, Azerbaijani scholars used Arabic in a high way along with the Persian language.

With the spread of Islam among large masses throughout the country, madrasahs (schools) located in large mosques began to operate in the cities of Azerbaijan. The Arabic and Persian languages, logic, religious dogmatics, fiqh (Islamic law), mathematics, calligra-

phy, history, and literature were taught in these madrasahs. Greek philosophy, astrology, logic, oratory, geometry, medicine, alchemy and the like were also taught in large madrasahs, similar to modern universities. Of course, there were no professional teachers, the ones who taught here were mostly theologians and clerics, and they were called mudarris (professors), and their assistants "muid" (assistant). The main method of teaching was rote learning, corporal punishment for children was acceptable.

In general, students of these schools were taught to read and write in Arabic, understand Arabic religious texts, and easily memorize the Holy Kuran. At least three years were devoted to Arabic grammar in madrasahs, and it was taught very deeply. There were also books regarding Arabic linguistics. In this way, students were brought to the level of being able to express themselves by freely answering questions in Arabic.

Education in madrasahs was based on the so-called deductive method. The fundamental of this method is adherence to scientists who have written works on certain topics and expressed their opinions on several issues. This method of education was carried out in the form of memorization, repetition, comprehension, discussion, and note-taking. Memorization was the basis of educational methodology.

According to G. Makdisi (1970), memorization was based on reciting a large amount of material, and interpreting and repeating it. Though memorization skill was very important in the medieval education system, comprehension and discussion were just as important as memorization. In fact, both comprehension and discussion seemed to support the notion of rote learning. Another tool used in educational methodology is taking notes. This tool, called a notebook, filled with knowledge and played the role of a helper in the restoration of a kind of "memory that became a storehouse of knowledge".

Arabic and Persian were two main languages till the occupation of Azerbaijan by Tsarist Russia. The occupation of Azerbaijan by Tsarist Russia in 1813 had a huge impact and a radical change on the economic, political and cultural life of Azerbaijanis because they were forced to integrate into Russian culture. In the 19th century, Tsarist Russia including the Caucasus area was already a single administrative territory and had a school administration based on a single law. Tsarist

Russia didn't have a strong education system, mostly military and private schools. Peter, I made some reforms due to the need for educated Russians. They established a network of primary school education in Tsarist Russia.

Developments regarding education in Tsarist Russia impacted Azerbaijan, too. A new district school was opened in Shusha in 1830. With the opening of the Shusha school, the foundation of European-style secular education was laid in Azerbaijan. In 1832, another district school was opened in Baku, and education at the school was in Russian, and Azerbaijani was taught as an additional subject. In 1849, a new type of educational institution - the Muslim school - was established in Baku, despite the name, it wasn't a traditional school and differed from the traditional religious madrasas.

Additionally, since the 1780s, a seminary system had been adopted in the Tsarist Russia. Based on that model, in the Caucasus, the Transcaucasian Teachers Seminary which specialized in teaching was founded in Gori, Georgia for the Caucasus people. Those who were interested in working teachers at regional primary schools attended the seminary. The school had a Tatar (Russians called Azerbaijanis and other Turkic-speaking people Tatar) section which was established in 1879 thanks to Mirza Fatali Akhundovs, an Azerbaijani writer, and activist. The Tatar department was attended only by Muslims and instructions were given for only primary schools in the Russian language.

From 1843 to 1917, public education in the Caucasus was managed by a single body - the Caucasian Education District, and all the rules defining the activities of the Caucasian peoples, including the various educational institutions in the region, were prepared by that body. Russian emperor Tsar Nicholas II wanted Russian to be prioritized over other native languages.

Ben Eklof (1991) describes schools of that period and mentions that the pedagogical system was child-centered and a large amount of homework caused cheating by students. Teachers gave many home tasks to students, as a result, learners had to copy-paste or ask help from parents to finish the tasks. The same strategies were also applied in Azerbaijan but with elements from the traditional way of teaching. Even now, many teachers are using the same strategy despite instructions from the Ministry of Science and Education, and consequence is again the same. The final outcome of this strategy is cheating by learners.

According to the census of 1897, only 21% of the population was literate in imperial Russia, and this number was especially low in the territories occupied by Tsarist Russia including Azerbaijan because it was a privilege for mostly affluent families to send their children to school.

The Russia Empire collapsed in 1917 after the revolution, and Azerbaijan gained its independence between the years 1918-1920. Baku State University, one of the main universities of Azerbaijan in modern times, was established in that period but it didn't last long. During this period, foreign teachers were invited to conduct lessons at the Baku State University. Probably teaching approaches and strategies were a little bit different in their classes but mostly it was the same with the Tsarist period because making radical changes over 2 years was impossible. Just the curricula were changed

and nationalized, and new textbooks and teaching materials were designed.

The Soviet troops occupied Azerbaijan again in 1920 and the Soviet system was established. During the Soviet time, Soviet authorities decided to abolish the use of the Arabic alphabet in the native languages of people in the Central Asia including the Caucasus. Thus, Russian language instruction intensified in the 1920s and became a compulsory learning language in 1938. Most universities required non-Russians to pass an admission examination in the Russian language and literature, so the incentive for learning Russian grew gradually. The teaching of the Russian language was of greater interest, and there were Russian-oriented schools. At the same time, during the Soviet period, the official languages in Azerbaijan were Azerbaijani and Russian. Therefore, the opportunities to use the Russian language and the interest in learning it were greater; also, one of the requirements for working in high-ranking positions was to know the Russian language fluently.

But this does not mean that the English language was neglected. The higher educational institutions of Azerbaijan started teaching foreign languages in the 1920s. In the 1930s and 1950s, English, French, and German were taught in the schools of the Soviet republics, as well as in Azerbaijan. In 1960, as the USSR tried to strengthen its foreign ties with other countries, foreign language teaching began to be of great importance. Thus, the Council of Ministers of the Soviet government signed a decree "on Improving Foreign Language" in Soviet Republics.

The main strategy used in the Soviet era was based on rote memorization, the classic method which is called "Grammar-translation" was applied in the teaching process in which, emphasis was placed on grammar and vocabulary, and there was a limited number of teaching aids because they were strictly controlled and monitored. The textbooks designed by local teachers didn't cover the skills of writing, reading, speaking, and listening. Even the section on listening was omitted in most of the textbooks because of the lack of classrooms equipped with the necessary facilities to implement listening activities. In the meantime, the activities given in the textbooks were mixed, not categorized and systematic. The use of materials outside the book was not allowed.

During classes, students should memorize vocabulary and grammar rules, read and translate texts, and answer questions based on the text. Speaking activities were mostly based on retelling texts, reciting poems and answering questions based on the text. The classroom culture in Soviet-era Azerbaijan also had defining characteristics. The teaching was strict and authoritative, and teachers were treated with great respect (Counts, 1961). Classes were teacher-centered; students should respect teachers and follow their classroom rules.

Implementation of innovative approaches, critical thinking, and students' autonomy in classes were out of the question. Grammatical accuracy was highly valued and every error made by the students was corrected and even criticized by the teacher, consequently, all these resulted in the discouragement and demotivation of students to speak English in classes.

English was not taught as a means of communication because it was not needed. It was taught by the local teachers who had never communicated with native speakers in English. Though the means of instruction was English, most teachers never used English during the teaching process. In a closed system like the Soviet, there was no need to communicate in English or other foreign languages, since people were not allowed to leave the country, they had no opportunity to speak English with foreigners and improve their level of language. It is for this reason that there was a lack of motivation among the learners and all this hindered the quality teaching of the language. As a result, many people could not speak English even though they had studied English for a long time during their school years.

In 1991, the Soviet system collapsed and Azerbaijan gained its independence. During the period of independence, many reforms were made in the education system. In the Soviet era, they started learning a foreign language from the 5th grade, since the period of independence it started to be taught in the 1st grade.

During the years of independence, many restrictions that were applied in Soviet time were removed. Course books have been further improved and they are updated and standardized now. Although the teaching materials are still designed by local teachers, modern examples are used as formats and models. All foreign language books are designed to teach 4 skills and classrooms to improve listening skills have been put into use in schools and universities.

The Ministry of Science and Education of Azerbaijan switched to the curriculum method in schools. The standardized curriculum is prepared by the Ministry of Science and Education and sent to schools. The curriculum methodology has the characteristics of the communicative method and aims to teach students English as a means of communication.

Despite all these reforms, there are still problems and challenges in foreign language teaching. It is difficult to change the approach of teachers who were educated and got used to the methodologies of the Soviet era. Regular training is arranged for them to teach the new methodologies and approaches to foreign language teaching and the requirements of the state but most of those teachers do not want to lose their dominance in the classroom by changing the teacher-centered approach to the student-centered approach. It means there is still a part of teachers who apply the "Grammar-translation" method but the new generation of teachers is more inclined to use a communicative method with strategies such as project-based learning, student-centered learning, apply innovations in the classrooms and approach lessons with critical thinking.

The teaching of foreign languages in universities is not regulated by the Ministry of Education but by the universities themselves. Universities are interested in

raising the quality of foreign language teaching, and foreign language teachers are free to design their own curricula and choose methods and teaching aids to utilize in classes. This gives them opportunities to make more changes and innovations and it is for this reason that the level of teaching foreign languages is higher in universities than in schools.

Regardless of all this, it will take some time to remove the Soviet-era ideologies from education, and there is a lot of work to be done in this way to move closer to West and Western education models.

Conclusion

Unlike other beings, humans have the ability to learn foreign languages, and this process started from early periods. People living in the close geographical area had to interact with others for different purposes such as trade, collecting information, etc. Thus, learning a second language was a necessity arising from the environment and different conditions. In that case, it was a natural phenomenon. Maybe not planned, and systematically but was enough to learn because the purpose was communication.

Harmer (1991) said: "Despite intense research efforts dedicated to finding out how people learn a foreign language, we still do not know for sure how the process occurs". As Harmer stated, effective teaching of foreign languages is still a mystery and needs further discussions and investigations. However, we can say for sure that if it is taught as a means of communication, activities, and methods used for that purpose will achieve their target to a certain extent because each human being has an ability to learn language not depending on their intelligence.

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